

Teaching about spatial navigation: some (inter)disciplinary insights

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Abstract

For researchers interested in Spatial Information Theory (SIT), sharing concepts, methods, and tools is a fundamental requirement for the advancement of interdisciplinary collaboration. However, topics related to SIT are still predominantly taught on a disciplinary basis at universities. In this exploratory study, we searched for the elements that are commonly shared among disciplines when teaching about a SIT-related topic such as spatial navigation. Non-directive interviews were conducted with five professors and lecturers from various academic fields at Université Laval (Quebec City, Canada). The goals, concepts, methods, and tools employed to teach about spatial navigation were analyzed using a reflexive thematic analysis framework. Highlights of the study concern the purpose of working on spatial navigation, the conceptual framework the students should know, and the pedagogical approach that is used. This exploratory study reveals that despite their diverse backgrounds, teaching professionals working on spatial navigation have much in common. These results open perspectives for developing teaching materials that could be shared across disciplines to train the future generation of SIT researchers from an interdisciplinary perspective.

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1 Introduction

Spatial Information Theory (SIT) is inherently interdisciplinary. However, this does not mean that interdisciplinary research is easy. One of the main challenges of interdisciplinary research is that researchers need to be able to share concepts, methods, and tools to collaborate despite their disciplinary backgrounds [10]. An interesting way of meeting this challenge could be to train future SIT researchers to understand the implications of interdisciplinarity from their university years. This is notably the aim promoted by interdisciplinary instruction. This pedagogical approach to teaching encourages students to work on large themes by incorporating several disciplinary perspectives [1] and should therefore enable them to develop reasoning skills [15], awareness, and collaborative attitudes [6] that are needed to tackle contemporary problems [13]. However, this approach is still rare in universities.

Among the areas of interest for SIT, spatial navigation is a good example of a topic that requires interdisciplinary collaboration. Spatial navigation can be defined as the process by which organisms use multiple cue sources and resources to determine and travel a route to a goal [5]. This topic brings together researchers from a wide range of disciplines, such as robotics, geomatics, or psychology [7]. Some recent publications have emphasized the need for a better interdisciplinary integration in spatial navigation, especially in the design of navigation aids. Hence, [8] argues that knowledge about spatial cognition should be more incorporated into the design of navigation systems. [14] also reports on this cognitive engineering approach and calls for the integration of insights from cartography, cognitive psychology, and human-computer interactions into the design of user-centered navigation assistance technologies. However, despite this need for interdisciplinary integration, the spatial navigation topic is still discussed on a disciplinary basis in universities rather than as a global theme incorporating these multiple perspectives. To our understanding, there is

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currently no documented initiative to teach about spatial navigation from an interdisciplinary perspective.

In this context, this exploratory study stands as the inaugural step in a project aimed at developing pedagogical tools to teach about spatial navigation from an interdisciplinary perspective. It proposes to take stock of the spatial navigation teaching of five professors and lecturers from various disciplines at Université Laval, Quebec City, Canada. This work aims to answer the following question: What are the common goals, concepts, methods, and tools that are shared among disciplines when dealing with spatial navigation? The answer to this question could provide interesting insights to lay the foundation of a pedagogical toolbox that could be shared across SIT-related fields. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, the population of interviewees, along with the interview and analysis methods, are detailed. Section 3 highlights the main results that are discussed in Section 4. Finally, a conclusion is provided in the last section.

2 Methodology

2.1 Interview methodology

To answer the central question of this study, a non-directive interview method proposed by [16] was used. It has been often tried-and-tested with education professionals. The initial question of the interview was: *What are the goals, concepts, methods, and tools you deal with when teaching students about spatial navigation?* This interview method was chosen to allow the interviewees to talk about everything they think was relevant to their consignments without interrupting. In cases where interviewees did not discuss all the dimensions of the question, non-inductive additional questions were used to ensure no part would be omitted. These consist of questions that are interested in *what* and *how* rather than *why* [12] and are therefore complementary to a non-directive approach. The author has special training in using this interview method and has already used it in previous work.

Five professors and lecturers were interviewed at Université Laval, a French-speaking university in Canada. Professors and lecturers were selected based on their disciplinary fields of expertise related to spatial navigation. Three of the interviewees were identified via the university courses' website. The other two interviewees were recruited via professional relationships. Each interviewee received an email inviting them to participate in this study. The interviews took place from December 2023 to February 2024. All interviewees were recorded with their consent. Table 1 shows the main interviewees' characteristics.

Profession	Faculty	Speciality
Lecturer	Urban Planning, Architecture and Design	Signage
Lecturer	Sciences and Engineering	Human-Computer Interf.
Lecturer	Forestry, Geography and Geomatics	Geography teaching
Professor	Forestry, Geography and Geomatics	Cognitive geomatics
Professor	Sciences and Engineering	Mobile robotics

■ **Table 1** Interviewees characteristics

2.2 Interview materials analysis

Interviews lasted an average of 65 min (Min = 30 min, max = 106 min). Interviews were transcribed extensively by hand. A reflexive thematic analysis was then conducted. Thematic analysis (TA) is an approach that focuses on identifying themes and trends in qualitative data, such as interview transcripts. Reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) is a form of thematic analysis that recognizes the researcher's influence on the outlined themes. This influence is discussed in Section 4. RTA involves six steps in order to refine the themes: 1/familiarization with data, 2/coding, 3/initial themes, 4/themes refinement, 5/theme consistency check, 6/analysis report. Table 2 shows the evolution of the themes over time (steps 3, 4, 5). According to [4], RTA is appropriate for datasets of around 4 to 5 interviews or more.

Initial themes	Refined themes	Resulting themes
Goals	Teaching purposes - Create routes - Create support	Spatial navigation purpose: - Efficiency - Autonomy - Universal accessibility
Concepts	Concepts - cognition - sensoriality - space - habits - emotions - others	Conceptual framework: - Agent - Environment - Context
Methods	Pedagogy - Doing - Thinking	Pedagogical approach: - Active Learning - Projects - Awareness improvement
Tools ⇒ Pedagogical ⇒ Applied		

■ **Table 2** Evolution of themes over RTA.

3 Results

Common themes were identified within the interview materials, related to: the purpose of working on spatial navigation; the conceptual framework the students should know; and the pedagogical approach that is mobilized by the teaching professionals.

3.1 What is the purpose of working on spatial navigation?

According to the interviewees, working on spatial navigation is oriented toward providing information. By providing agents with the appropriate levels and types of information, a two-fold purpose is pursued: building a framework that supports navigation efficiency while supporting agents' autonomy in the environment. For all the interviewees, providing a frame (often called a route (in French, *itinéraire* or *parcours*)) to get from A to B with efficiency is at the core of spatial navigation. Efficiency has several meanings for them. The most common is that agents should be able to find and get to their destination in an unfamiliar environment. But two other meanings of efficiency were also mentioned: temporal efficiency, that is about getting to destination without wasting time, and situational efficiency, that is

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about ensuring the agent's peace of mind along the route by reducing risk and stress. All these meanings of efficiency require thinking about what information to be provided, how it should be formatted and how it should be delivered so that agents will be able to take the right actions at the right time.

Working on spatial navigation also involves helping agents be self-reliant on the environment. Autonomy in the environment is based on two components, according to the interviewees: facilitating the building of internal representations of the environment and providing information that is accessible to all. The internal representations (often called mental maps) should help agents not become dependent on the frame suggested to them. Thereby, they could overcome uncertainty and/or increase their efficiency by identifying shortcuts. To tackle this objective, the level and format of information should enable agents to infer additional information about the environment while avoiding overload. Accessibility, for its parts, is mostly related here to the selection of meaningful colors, icons, and locations of information so that everyone can see and understand it.

This two-fold purpose of framing a route and supporting autonomy sounds like a challenge for the interviewees. To help students overcome this challenge, teaching professionals provide them with a conceptual framework and a pedagogical approach to help them implement relevant navigation supports for agents.

3.2 What is the conceptual framework students should know?

Based on the interview materials, some recurrent concepts were identified, as well as links between them, which consist of a kind of framework. This spatial navigation conceptual framework integrates three main components: the agent, the environment, and the context.

Agent: As stated in Section 3.1, working on spatial navigation seems mostly about providing information to support navigation. This information-oriented approach requires understanding how agents perceive and understand their environment in order to adopt the most effective strategy for the provision of information. Access to understanding mechanisms and internal representations of the agents is, however, difficult because each agent is unique and such inner processes and information are not easy to catch.

Understanding the environment appears to be largely dependent on some cognitive components, perception, and language for the interviewees. The two cognitive components they discussed most were memory and reasoning abilities (either spatial or non-spatial). These components are said to support the comprehension of information and the formation of effective internal representations, as they help agents draw connections between what they know from memory and what they perceive in the environment. Concerning perception, vision appears to be the dominant sensory modality for spatial navigation. Integration of multisensory cues (auditory, haptic, olfactory, or proprioceptive) is, however, promoted as an effective way of reinforcing spatial information comprehension and memorization. Language is also a major theme in the interviews, as it is central to providing navigation instructions. Language is, however, said to be ambiguous, which is why some interviewees prefer to rely on graphical elements when communicating information about the environment.

Environment: For the interviewees, the environment supports the agents' understanding of navigation information and the building of internal representations in several ways. First are decision points (also called landmarks) that are parts of the environment that support decision-making. Decision points are said to have two common characteristics: they are visually prominent compared to the surrounding environment, and they are related to an action that the agent needs to take along the route. The structure of space also gives agents clues to help them understand the environment and navigate. Spatial structures — whether

it is a screen layout or the arrangement of streets or corridors — communicate an idea of a spatial hierarchy that helps agents understand information and organize their internal representations. Navigating in open spaces seems to be more difficult than navigating in structured ones, so creating artificial structures sounds like a good strategy for navigation in such places, according to the teaching professionals.

It is interesting to note that four of the five interviewees emphasized that decision points and structures are part of a spatial as well as a temporal referential. For example, in order to deliver relevant route information from A to B, the temporal order and the temporal precision of the information need to match the spatial dimension of the decision points and structures. This was especially highlighted when discussing applications like Google Maps with their set of turn-by-turn instructions, which were frequently quoted as examples.

Context: The agent-environment interaction depends on context, which refers here to the social, cultural, and emotional factors. Relying on social habits appears to be an effective strategy to guide agents through the environment, as it leverages the reflexes they have and reduces the resources they need to process information. This is directly related to the importance of memory (see above). Cultural dimensions also play a role in the agent-environment interaction. Depending on the country, space may be structured differently. For the interviewees, this has implications for spatial navigation and ties in with the importance of spatial structures (see above). The way information is understood may also differ across cultures and is related to accessibility and language themes.

When considering the agent individually, emotions, familiarity with a place, and attachment to a place are three factors that may affect how information is processed and incorporated into an agent's internal representations of the environment. Depending on an individual's state of mind and personal history, the focus on information or the connections made to what is stored in memory may vary. Among emotions, stress was the most commonly cited by the interviewees, and time pressure was the most commonly reported stress source. This may be related to the interviewees' shared conceptualization of spatial navigation, which includes both spatial and temporal dimensions.

3.3 What is the pedagogical approach used?

All the interviewees mobilize active learning methods to help students understand the purpose of working on spatial navigation and the conceptual framework they are presented with. Mostly, students are invited to work on projects, in groups or individually, and produce navigation supports (signs, maps, apps, instructions, etc.). Hence, they have to demonstrate, through concrete production, that they are able to integrate various insights to conceive, implement, and deliver adequate navigation information.

The benefits of hands-on projects are twofold here: they make students practice and apply the disciplinary insights they were taught during the course (relating to computer science, design, geography, etc.), but they also (and maybe foremost) lead them to be more aware of the challenge of working on spatial navigation by experiencing by themselves the importance of taking into consideration all the concepts related to agent, environment, and context. Projects are, according to the interviewees, mostly made to raise awareness among the students by relying on their own experience.

4 Discussion

None of the interviewees mentioned the word *interdisciplinarity*. However, they did share concerns about integrating concepts from several disciplinary fields and discussed pedagogical

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approaches aiming to develop students comprehension and awareness. At the heart of their concerns lies a challenge: how to help agents navigate a route from A to B efficiently while simultaneously building an internal representation of the environment that promotes their autonomy. This challenge of providing effective guidance while simultaneously building rich internal representations is a central theme for spatial navigation research, especially when it comes to navigation assistive technologies [11].

Tackling this challenge requires an understanding of what is at stake during the course of spatial navigation and, therefore, insights from various disciplines. Because the goal of the interviewees seemed mostly oriented toward training students to conceive and implement navigation supports delivering adequate information, they called mostly on operational concepts, coming from cognitive psychology (ex. mental maps), human-computer interaction (ex. multi-sensory inputs), or geography (ex. spatial referential), rather than on a deep understanding of the mechanisms underpinning spatial navigation. This suggests that the interviewees share a common set of multidisciplinary concepts, despite their disciplinary roots. None of the interviewees used the word *framework*, but the interactions between the concepts seem to form a cohesive system for them. It is important to mention the importance of elements such as decision points, spatio-temporal accuracy, place attachment, or multi-sensory perception in the speeches, as they are related to recent research focusing on how landmarks, context, or multi-sensory integration influence spatial knowledge acquisition (see, e.g., [9]). This underlines how close nowadays' research and teaching concerns are.

Active-learning approaches and methods seem to be at the heart of the teaching about spatial navigation. Case-based projects, in particular, are promoted by all the interviewees to help students integrate concepts and develop awareness through hands-on practice. This is a well-known pedagogical practice aiming to encourage involvement and reflexivity by providing students with some independence and higher-order thinking [3]. Given the trend towards more experience-based pedagogy in higher education [2], it is however difficult to determine how much this active learning approach to spatial navigation relies on concerns for a more interdisciplinary perspective among the interviewees.

Since this exploratory study employs a reflexive thematic analysis approach, it is important to recognize that the author's background may have shaped the outlined themes. The author comes from an interdisciplinary background and works in an interdisciplinary context that may have, in particular, drawn the author's attention toward specific concepts related to cognition, human-computer interactions, and geography. Also, this study comes with some limitations. The main one is that some relevant disciplines are missing. For example, no teaching professionals from psychology or ethology have been identified to be part of this study. This has contributed to focusing on spatial navigation from an information-oriented perspective rather than on themes related to navigation behavior, for instance.

5 Conclusion

This exploratory study aimed to search for the elements that are shared among disciplines when teaching about spatial navigation at Université Laval, Quebec City, Canada. Interview materials were collected among five teaching professionals dealing with spatial navigation. A reflexive thematic analysis was then done. It highlighted that spatial navigation was perceived as a challenging topic, consisting of both providing information to ensure efficient navigation and supporting autonomy through the development of internal representations of the environment. To help students deal with this topic, teaching professionals relied on an agent-environment-context framework, integrating concepts from various disciplines. They

also used active-learning methods to raise students' awareness about the complexity of the topic of spatial navigation.

These results suggest that there is room for an interdisciplinary approach in this academic context. It is also worthy to note that many dimensions of teaching echo actual research topics, which could provide an opportunity for better integration between recent scientific findings and teaching. As a next step, these common elements will be leveraged to create some hands-on projects' scenarios about spatial navigation that will be used in a course about cognition and space to be open to the graduate students at Université Laval. These (inter)disciplinary insights could also lay the foundation of what could become a toolbox for teaching and learning about spatial navigation to be shared across the SIT community.

References

- 1 Keith C. Barton and Lynne A. Smith. Themes or motifs? aiming for coherence through interdisciplinary outlines. *The Reading Teacher*, 54(1):54–63, 2000.
- 2 S. Adams Becker and M. Cummins. The nmc horizon report: 2017 higher education edition. Technical report, The New Media Consortium, 2017.
- 3 Charles C. Bonwell and James A. Eison. Active learning: creating excitement in the classroom. Technical report, The George Washington University, School of Education and Human Development., 1991.
- 4 Virginia Braun and Victoria Clark. Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, 11(4):589–597, 2019. doi:10.1080/2159676X.2019.1628806.
- 5 David R. Broadbeck and Stéphanie E. Tanninen. *Encyclopedia of the Sciences of Learning*, chapter Place Learning and Spatial Navigation. Springer, 2012.
- 6 Ana M. Corbacho, Ludia Minini, and Mariana Pereyra. Interdisciplinary higher education with a focus on academic motivation and teamwork diversity. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 2:100062, 2021. doi:10.1016/j.ijedro.2021.100062.
- 7 Michel Denis. *Petit traité de l'espace : un parcours pluridisciplinaire*. MARDAGA, 2016.
- 8 Elise Grison and Valérie Gyselinck. La cognition spatiale pour repenser les aides à la navigation. *L'année psychologique*, 119(2):243–278, 2019. doi:10.3917/anpsy1.192.0243.
- 9 Sara Lanini-Maggi, Christopher Hilton, and Sara I. Fabrikant. Limiting the reliance on navigation assistance with navigation instructions containing emotionally salient narratives for confident wayfinding. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 91:102151, 2023. doi:10.1016/j.jenvp.2023.102151.
- 10 Fulvio Mazzocchi. Scientific research across and beyond disciplines: Challenges and opportunities of interdisciplinarity. *EMBO Reports*, 20(e47682), 2019. doi:10.15252/embr.201947682.
- 11 Daniel R. Montello. Cognitive research in giscience: Recent achievements and future prospects. *Geography Compass*, 3(5):1824–1840, 2009. doi:10.1111/j.1749-8198.2009.00273.x.
- 12 Claire Petitmengin. Describing one's subjective experience in the second person: An interview method for the science of consciousness. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, 5(3–4):229–269, 2006. doi:10.1007/s11097-006-9022-2.
- 13 Allen F. Repko. *Interdisciplinary Research: Process and Theory*. SAGE, 2008.
- 14 Ian T. Ruginski, Nicholas A. Giudice, Sarah Creem-Regehr, and Toru Ishikawa. Designing mobile spatial navigation systems from the user's perspective: an interdisciplinary review. *Spatial Cognition and Computation*, 22(1):1–29, 2022. doi:10.1080/13875868.2022.2053382.
- 15 Elisabeth J. H. Spelt, Harm J. A. Biemans, Hilde Tobi, Pieter A. Luning, and Martin Mulder. Teaching and learning in interdisciplinary higher education: A systematic review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 21:365–378, 2009. doi:10.1007/s10648-009-9113-z.
- 16 Catherine Yelnik. L'entretien clinique de recherche en sciences de l'éducation. *Recherche et formation*, 50:133–146, 2005.